

USING AN ORDINAL RANKING RULE TO FIND THE TOP-PERFORMING GAUSSIAN MIXTURE MODELS FOR LANGUAGE RECOGNITION

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Abstract— In previous work [1], we developed a method for finding the top-performing Gaussian mixture models for the language recognition. This method orders the models from best-performing to worst-performing using calculated dispersion measures. Multiple dispersion measurements are used to produce multiple rankings of the models, which are combined to produce a ranking from which the top-performing models can be extracted. This method has reduced model testing time, since researchers can determine the top-performing models without evaluating the entire population of models. In this paper we demonstrate the ability of our ranking rule to find the top-performing models for different data sets and performance measures. The performance of our ranking rule is also compared to existing ordinal ranking rules: Kohler [2], Arrow & Raynaud [2], Borda [3], and Copeland [3].

Index Terms— Gaussian mixture models, Language Recognition, Ordinal Ranking Rules, Rank Aggregation.

1. INTRODUCTION

Gaussian Mixture Models (GMM) with shifted delta cepstra (SDC) features are popular for language recognition. GMM performance depends on four SDC parameters used during the training of the models ([4], [5]). Any tool that generates many SDC configurations can be used to search for models that yield high performing language recognition. Search time can be very lengthy, because hundreds of parameter sets may be generated, and for each parameter set models are trained and tested. Model performance also depends on how well the training data matches the evaluation data, and the performance measure used to evaluate the models. The use of detection error tradeoff (DET) curves is most popular for evaluating the language recognition performance models. DET curves require recognition scores from significant amounts of evaluation data. Measurements such as equal error rate (EER), area under the DET curve (AUD), or detection cost function (CDET) are calculated from the DET curve points and used to assess the performance of the model set (Definitions for these performance measurements can be found in [6]). For confidence in performance measures, the evaluation set needs hundreds of files. The complexities of model testing (e.g. time, costly data) provide our motivation to use an alternative method for finding top-performing models.

We previously developed a method largely based on distance. A detailed explanation of our ranking rule can be found in [1] and [7]. This rule was developed on the assumption that a set of GMMs with large dispersion between class models will have better recognition performance than a set of GMMs with small dispersion measure between class models parameters. A large dispersion measure should indicate the class models are located far apart in model space, thus reducing the number of errors during the recognition process.

Our proposed rule was developed using 277 model sets, which are varied SDC parameters. Our proposed rule uses three distance measurements (Bhattacharyya Shape [8], Symmetric Kullback-Leibler Divergence [9], and Reynolds [8]) to produce three dispersion measure rankings of the models. These rankings are combined to form a refined ranking, which we sometimes refer to as the compromise ranking, from which the top-performing models can be determined. In [1] we show that our ranking can identify the top-performing N% models, where N was varied from 10% to 90% in increments of 10%, with 100% recall for the 1996 National Institute of Standard and Technology (NIST) language recognition evaluations (LRE) development data [10] when EER is the performance measure. In other words, our ranking rule produces the EER ranking of the 1996 data. This ability reduces model test time, since researchers can determine the top-performing models without evaluating the entire population of models

This paper demonstrates the ability of our ranking rule to determine the top-performing models for the 2003 and 2005 NIST LRE data ([11],[12]) when different performance measures are used. The performance of our ranking rule is also compared to existing ordinal ranking methods: Kohler [2], Arrow & Raynaud [2], Borda [3] and Copeland ([3]). Section 2 provides a description of the Gaussian mixture models and experimental data, Section 3 describes our ordinal ranking rule, Section 4 presents the experimental results, and section 5 provides conclusions.

2. BACKGROUND

2.1 Gaussian Mixture Models

Gaussian mixture models are popular in a variety of recognition areas because of their ability to represent

multimodal densities. A Gaussian mixture model is the sum of weighted multivariate Gaussian density functions of the form:

$$p(\mathbf{x} | \lambda) = \sum_{i=1}^M \rho_i b_i(\mathbf{x}), \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{x} is a feature vector, λ is the class model, M is the mixture order, ρ_i is the mixture weight,

$$b_i(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{1}{(2\pi)^{D/2} |\Sigma_i|^{1/2}} e^{-\frac{1}{2}(\mathbf{x}-\boldsymbol{\mu}_i)^T \Sigma_i^{-1} (\mathbf{x}-\boldsymbol{\mu}_i)}. \quad (2)$$

A GMM for each class is completely defined by the mixture weights, $\boldsymbol{\rho}$, mean vectors, $\boldsymbol{\mu}$, and covariance matrices, Σ , for each component density. These parameters are usually represented by λ , i.e.

$$\lambda = \{\rho_i, \boldsymbol{\mu}_i, \Sigma_i, i=1, \dots, M\}. \quad (3)$$

We used these parameters in our distance measurements.

2.2 Data Description

The Gaussian mixture models were trained using the Callfriend corpus [5]. The 1996, 2003, and 2005 NIST language recognition evaluations (LRE) were used for testing the Gaussian mixture models. The following sections describe both the training and testing data.

2.2.1. Model Training Data

The Callfriend corpus training partition consists of 30-minute conversation sides for each of the following twelve languages: Arabic, English, Farsi, French, German Mandarin, Spanish, Hindi, Japanese, Korean, Tamil, and Vietnamese. We trained models for each of the 12 languages in the Callfriend corpus.

2.2.2. Model Evaluation Data

The 1996 and 2003 NIST LRE data sets contain 3-, 10-, and 30-second speech segments from the 12 languages. The 2005 NIST LRE data set consists of 3-, 10-, and 30-second speech segments from the 7 languages: English, Hindi, Japanese, Korean, Mandarin, Spanish, Tamil. We tested the models using each of these data sets.

2.2.3. Performance Measurements

For each evaluation data set, Detection Error Tradeoff (DET) curves were computed for the models. Two performance measures were extracted from the DET Curves: (1) Equal Error Rate (EER), defined as the point on the DET curve where the probability of a false alarm (Pf) equals the probability of a miss (Pm) and (2) probability of a false alarm occurring when the probability of miss equals 0.1 (PFPM0.1).

3. ORDINAL RANKING RULE

3.1 Gaussian Mixture Model Dispersion

We experimented with sets of GMMs produced by an experiment to find better feature vectors. We used 277 model

sets in our experiments. Each set contains twelve classes of 512-mixture models ($M = 512$). To determine the dispersion measure for a model set, the distance between every pair of class models was computed (i.e. ${}^{12}C_2 = 66$ distances per set). We used *the sum of these 66 distances as the dispersion measure* for each model set. The GMM sets were then ranked according to their dispersion measure, producing a *dispersion measure ranking*. A detailed description of how to compute the dispersion measure can be found [7]. For our experiments, three distance measurements are used to produce three dispersion measure rankings of the models that we shown in [7] to be useful: Reynolds, Kullback-Leibler Divergence, and Bhattacharyya Shape.

3.2 Ordinal Ranking Rule

Ordinal ranking methods are used to form a compromise ranking among multiple criteria on a set of alternatives. The only requirement for an ordinal ranking method is the rank order of the alternatives for each criterion is known. In our case, the multiple criteria are the three dispersion measure rankings, and the alternatives are the model sets.

We utilize an outranking matrix to form a compromise ranking among the multiple dispersion measure rankings. An outranking matrix, M_{ij} , is a simple representation of pairwise contests between alternatives, a_i and a_j . Every coefficient in this matrix represents the total number of pairwise contests won by alternative a_i against a_j , according to the rankings. A coefficient of zero means none of the rankings prefer one alternative to another, and a coefficient greater than zero indicates the number of rankings that prefer one alternative to another. For example, suppose a set of n alternatives $A = \{a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n\}$ are ranked by q voters which produce q rankings (r_1, r_2, \dots, r_q) . An $n \times n$ outranking matrix M , of a_i over a_j ($1 \leq i \leq n, 1 \leq j \leq n$) is defined by

$$M_{ij} = \sum_{k=1}^q R_k(a_i, a_j), \quad \text{for } i \neq j, \quad (4)$$

where M_{ij} represents the total number of rankings where a_i is ranked before a_j , $R_k(a_i, a_j) = 1$ if a_i is ranked before a_j by the k^{th} ranking, and $R_k(a_i, a_j) = 0$ if a_j is ranked before a_i by the k^{th} ranking. In short, this equation is simply counting the number of rankings that prefer a_i to a_j . Each row in the outranking matrix displays the number of pairwise contests won by a particular alternative against the other alternatives.

At iteration r , our proposed rule looks at the weighted sum of the two best ranks (the two maximum elements along each row of the outranking matrix M_{ij}) for each alternative, a_i , finds the alternative that has the highest weighted sum; and places that alternative in rank r of the compromise ranking. Weighting the maximums should alleviate ties; however, if there are ties one is chosen arbitrarily. The selected alternative is eliminated as a possibility for other ranks in the compromise ranking, and this entire procedure is repeated until all alternatives are eliminated. Below is a step by step description of the proposed rule.

TABLE 1

RANKING RULES AND LOWEST N (%) NEEDED TO FIND THE 10 TOP-PERFORMING MODELS FOR ALL FOR ALL DATA SETS AND PERFORMANCE MEASURES

Data Set	Ranking Rules with Lowest N (%)
A (1996 EER)	Our Proposed Rule (10) Kullback-Leibler (20), Bhattacharyya (20), Kohler (20) Borda (20), Copeland (20) Reynolds (30), Arrow & Raynaud (30)
B (2003 PFFPM)	Our Proposed Rule (60), Copeland (60) Reynolds (70), Borda (70) Kullback-Leibler (80), Bhattacharyya (80), Kohler (80) Arrow & Raynaud (80)
C (2003 PFFPM)	Bhattacharyya (70), Reynolds (70) Kullback-Leibler (80), Kohler (80), Arrow & Raynaud (80) Our Proposed Rule (90), Borda (90), Copeland (90)
D (2005 EER)	Our Proposed Rule (60), Bhattacharyya (60), Borda (60), Copeland (60) Reynolds (70), Kullback-Leibler (70), Kohler (70) Arrow & Raynaud (70)
E (2005 PFFPM)	Bhattacharyya(40) Kullback-Leibler (50), Kohler (50), Arrow & Raynaud(50) Reynolds (60) Our Proposed Rule (90), Borda (90), Kohler (90)

Step 1: Initialize $r = 1$.

Step 2: Identify the two maximum values along each row, i , of the outranking matrix, M_{ij} .

Step 3: Multiply the first maximum, $Max_i(1)$, by the chosen weight, w_1 , multiply the second maximum, $Max_i(2)$, by the chosen weight, w_2 , and sum the weighted maximums to obtain,

$$Weighted\ Sum = w_1 Max_i(1) + w_2 Max_i(2) \quad (5)$$

Step 4: Select the row, k with the highest weighted sum. Weighting the maximums should alleviate ties; however, if there are ties choose one arbitrarily. This row is the location of the alternative, a_k that will be assigned a rank of r in the compromise ranking.

Step 5: Delete the row and column (k) corresponding to the selected alternative.

Step 6: In $r < n$ then go to step 2, otherwise stop- since all alternatives have been ranked.

For our experiments, we used $w_1 = 2/3$ and $w_2 = 1/3$.

4. EXPERIMENT RESULTS

Three dispersion measure rankings, obtained by the Reynolds [8], Bhattacharyya Shape [8] and KL-Divergence [9] distance measurements, were used to produce an outranking matrix. Since each ranking consists of 277 model sets, a 277 by 277 outranking matrix was generated. Our rule used this outranking matrix to produce a compromise ranking. Other compromise rankings were produced using Kohler [2], Arrow & Raynaud [2], Borda [3], and Copeland [3] (Note Borda and Copeland do not utilize an outranking matrix to form a compromise ranking). Each compromise ranking was evaluated based on the lowest percentage of model evaluations required to find the top-performing 10 models. For example, one may have to evaluate at least 20% of the compromise ranking to identify the top-performing 10 model sets. In other words, the top-performing 10 models can be found by evaluating the top 55 ranked (20% of 277) model sets in the compromise ranking.

Table 1 displays each ranking rule with the lowest value of N (%) model evaluations required to find the top-performing 10 models for each data set and performance measure. The table is organized as follows. The first column lists the data sets which are: **A** – represents the 1996 equal error rate (EER) results, **B** – represents the 2003 EER results, **C** – represents the 2003 Probability of a false alarm and probability of a miss (PFFPM0.1) results, **D** – represents the 2005 EER results, and **E** – represents the 2005 PFFPM0.1 results. The second column lists the ranking rules and lowest N (%) required to find the top-performing 10 models for each data set. The ranking rules are listed from best to worst according to N (%). Note N is the value between the parentheses beside the ranking rules.

As Table 1 shows, for the 1996 data set with EER as the performance measure, our proposed rule identifies the top-performing 10 models with a lowest N value of 10%. In other words, the top 10% of the ranking produced by our proposed rule contains the top-performing 10 models. However, since the ranking of our proposed rule matches the 1996 EER ranking, its' top 10 ranked model sets are the top-performing 10 models. Therefore, our proposed rule identifies the top-performing 10 models independent of N for the 1996 NIST LRE data. For the 2003 data with EER as the performance measure, our proposed rule and Copeland identify the top-performing 10 models with a lowest N value of 60%. For the 2003 data with PFFPM0.1 as the performance measure, the Bhattacharyya Shape and Reynolds outperform the other rules with a lowest N value of 70%. Our proposed rule did not yield a comparable N ; however, using it to identify the top-performing 10 models still reduces the percentage of model evaluations (as we will show later). For the 2005 data with EER as the performance measure, our proposed rule, Bhattacharyya Shape, Borda, and Copeland identify the top-performing 10 models with a lowest N value of 60%. For the 2005 data with PFFPM0.1 as the performance measure, Bhattacharyya Shape outperforms the other rules with a lowest N value of 40%. Our proposed rule did not yield a comparable N ; however, using it to identify the top 10 models still reduces the percentage of model evaluations (as we will show later).

Table 1 was used to calculate the reduction K (%) in model evaluations for all ranking rules if they were used in place of the traditional evaluation step to identify the top-performing 10 models. The traditional evaluation step involves testing the entire population of models. Replacing this step with our proposed rule reduces the percentage of models that need testing. The reduction, K , is calculated for each ranking rule as:

$$K = 100\% - N_{MIN}, \quad (6)$$

where N_{MIN} is the lowest percentage of model evaluations required to find the top-performing 10 models. These reductions are shown in Figure 1 for all rankings rules, data sets, and performance measures. The x-axis represents the data sets and performance measures, and the y-axis represents K for each ranking rule.

Fig. 1: The Reduction K (%) in Model Evaluations for all Data Sets and Performance Measures

As Figure 1 shows, for the 1996 data set with EER as the performance measure, our proposed rule, labeled as ‘Bailey’, yields the highest reduction in model evaluations. It reduces percentage of model evaluations by 96% if used to find the top-performing 10 models. For the 2003 data with EER as the performance measure, our proposed rule and Copeland have the highest reductions. Employing them to find the top-performing 10 models reduces the percentage of model evaluations by approximately 40%. For the 2003 data with PFFPM0.1 as the performance measure, the Bhattacharyya Shape and Reynolds yield the highest reductions. Using them as a means to find the top-performing 10 models reduces percentage of model evaluations by roughly 30%. For the 2005 data with EER as the performance measure, our rule, Bhattacharyya Shape, Borda, and Copeland reduces the percentage of model evaluations by 40% if used as a means to find the top-performing 10 models. For the 2005 data with PFFPM0.1 as the performance measure, the Bhattacharyya Shape reduces the percentage of model evaluations by approximately 60% if used as a means to find the top-performing 10 models.

5. CONCLUSIONS

We assessed the performance of our ranking rule based on the percentage of model evaluations it requires for finding the top-performing 10 models out of 277 models. When EER is the performance measure, our proposed rule consistently finds the top-performing 10 models with the least percentage of model evaluations regardless of the data set. Other ranking rules also find the top-performing 10 models with model evaluation percentage as low as our rule; however, they are not consistent. When PFFPM0.1 is the performance measure,

our proposed rule does not show superior results. However, it still yields comparable results.

We confirmed our proposed rule yields the highest reduction in model evaluations for 1996 and 2003 NIST LRE data, when EER is the performance measure, if tasked to find the top-performing 10 models. For the 2005 NIST LRE data, when EER is the performance measure, our proposed rule is among those that yield high reduction in model evaluations. When PFFPM0.1 is the performance measure, our proposed rule does not yield superior reductions for the 2003 and 2005 NIST LRE data. However, we show did that it is still useful in reducing the percentage of model evaluations if used to find the top-performing 10 models.

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